

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF INFORMATION COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT IN STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10897666>

Аннотация: В данной статье описаны научно-теоретические основы развития информационно-технологических компетенций и профессиональной подготовки студентов педагогических высших учебных заведений. В статье раскрыты методические основы обеспечения будущих педагогов педагогическими условиями, формирования их профессиональных компетенций и организации профессиональной деятельности.

Ключевые слова: педагогика, высшее образование, информатика, компетентность, профессиональная компетентность, информационная компетентность.

Abstract: This article describes the scientific-theoretical foundations of the development of information technology competences and professional training of students in higher educational institutions of pedagogy. The article explains the methodological foundations of providing future pedagogues with pedagogical conditions, forming their professional competences and organizing their professional activities.

Key words: pedagogy, higher education, informatics, competence, professional competence, information competence,

In this article, we will first of all consider the theoretical problems of the development of student competencies in pedagogic HEIs, because in the diversity of approaches and opinions, two extreme points of view can be distinguished: the competent approach is a new paradigm of complete education and the competent approach is an is a modification of the traditional "knowledge paradigm".

All conditions for the formation of competencies can be divided into two groups. In the first group, we include those whose needs are expressed "from outside": the requirements of society, employers and the labor market. The main requirement of employers to the competencies of students and workers is the efficiency of the work they perform, as well as their behavioral characteristics

during work. The second group includes conditions implemented in the educational system, psychology, theory and methodology of professional education and other fields of knowledge. Our research is aimed at solving the problem of developing students' competence, and therefore it focuses more on the conditions that we classify as the second group.

In our research, as the first condition for the development of problems related to competencies, we defined the praxeological approach, because it is the praxeological characteristics of the employee that reflect the requirements of the labor market and employers.

The history of the formation of praxeology is presented in the studies of I.A. Kolesnikova and Ye.V. Titova. The concept of "praxeology" was first used in the 19th century by the French philosopher and historian L. Espinas. He suggested the creation of a separate scientific discipline that studies the factors that increase the effectiveness and usefulness of actions. The term "praxeology" became widespread as the science of the most general forms and principles of movement in the world of living beings.

In our opinion, in the theory and practice of education, much attention is traditionally paid to the formation of mental actions and, accordingly, to the study of this process. As we can see, the implementation of a competent approach makes it possible to take into account the second aspect we named in the preparation process - the aspect of practical action. This opinion is confirmed by the analysis of different interpretations of the concept of "competence".

A.M. Gurevich's research provides the following list of competence interpretations:

- it is a characteristic of the person to be evaluated, related to effective activity;
- this is an individual characteristic that helps to perform high-quality work in a certain position in the conditions of a certain organization;
- behavioral aspects affecting performance;
- these are any individual characteristics that can be measured or considered reliable, and it can be argued that they are important for the effective or ineffective performance of the work;
- these are the basic and potential abilities necessary for the quality performance of a certain job;
- all these are work-related personal characteristics, knowledge, skills and values that motivate a person to do his job well;

- this is the main personal characteristic that leads to effective or high results at work;

- this is a set of behavioral characteristics necessary for an employee to successfully perform a certain job (50, pp. 11-13).

There are also a number of definitions of competence in Internet sources:

- sufficient or adequate qualification, ability;

- sufficient or adequate physical or intellectual qualities;

- the ability to be qualified;

- the ability to do something well or according to a standard, obtained as a result of experience or training;

- the ability to be competent and able to perform a specific role, including knowledge, skills, behavior.

If we analyze the formulas of competencies included in the State Education Standards (DTS) from the point of view of the provided definitions, they reflect all the listed approaches. The main characteristics of competence, which we determined based on the analysis of the essence of the given interpretations and the praxeological approach, are as follows: first, competences are specific characteristics of effective professional activity or professional behavior; secondly, they should be measurable, observable and understandable both for those evaluating the subject of activity and for the subject himself; thirdly, competence is related to the specific activity of an employee in a certain organizational environment.

When talking about the problems of the formation of competencies of a modern specialist, it is impossible not to dwell on the problem of the relationship between the concepts of "competence" and "competence". There are a number of points of view on this issue. In the book "Handbook of Competencies" by S. Widdet and S. Halliford: "The ability needed to solve work problems and obtain the required work results is often a competence

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